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Assessment of vine shoots and surplus grape must for succinic acid bioproduction

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Abstract: Vine shoots and surplus grape must were assessed as feedstocks for succinic acid production with *Actinobacillus succinogenes* and *Basfia succiniproducens*. After acidic and enzymatic hydrolysis, vine shoots released 35-40 g/L total sugars. Both bacterial species produced 18-21 g/L succinic acid from this hydrolysate in 120 h. Regarding grape must fermentation, *A. succinogenes* clearly outperformed *B. succiniproducens*. Yeast extract was the only additional nutrient needed by *A. succinogenes* to grow on grape must. Under mathematically optimized conditions (145.7 g/L initial sugars and 24.9 g/L yeast extract), *A. succinogenes* generated 88.9 ± 1.4 g/L succinic acid in 96 h, reaching a succinic acid yield of 0.66 ± 0.01 g/g and a sugar consumption of 96.64 ± 0.30 %. Substrate inhibition was not observed in grape musts with 125-150 g/L initial sugars, provided that an adequate amount of yeast extract was available for bacteria. Alternative nitrogen sources to yeast extract (red wine lees, white wine lees, urea, NH₄Cl and choline chloride) were not suitable for *A. succinogenes* in grape must.

Keywords: Succinic acid; winery waste; fermentation; nitrogen source.

Abbreviations: AA: acetic acid; E: ethanol; FA: formic acid; LA: lactic acid; SA: succinic acid.

1. Introduction

Succinic acid is a dicarboxylic acid with numerous industrial applications, which is also used as a platform chemical for the synthesis of other compounds [1, 2]. It is mainly produced by a petrochemical route through the catalytic hydrogenation of maleic anhydride derived from butane. Nevertheless, the ability of certain rumen bacteria to produce succinic acid from a variety of carbon sources has encouraged the research on succinic acid bioproduction during the last decades [1-3]. In addition, since the United States Department of Energy classified succinic acid as an interesting building block that might be obtained from biomass in biorefineries [4], several companies have attempted its bioproduction on an industrial scale with very different fortunes [1, 5, 6]. To the best of our knowledge, only Roquette, BASF and PTT-MCC Biochem keep their facilities open for biosuccinic acid production [7-9]. *Actinobacillus succinogenes* and *Basfia succiniproducens* are the most efficient wild bacteria producing succinic acid. The main drawbacks of this bioproduction process are related to feedstock prices, production of secondary metabolites, auxotrophy, pH sensitivity, lack of appropriate genetic tools, NADH limitation and product inhibition [3].

Current commercial bioproduction of organic acids employs refined sugars, starch or molasses as feedstocks [10]. However, the use of alternative carbon sources could reduce production costs. Accordingly, industrial, agriculture and food by-products have been explored recently for succinic acid bioproduction [1, 3, 11].

Vine shoots (*Vitis vinifera* L.) are the most abundant by-product from the winery industry and they are generated during pruning activities at a rate of 1.4-2.0 t/ha [12]. Considering that 7,453,532 ha were devoted to vines in 2016 worldwide [13]; vine shoots constitute an interesting lignocellulosic resource in wine-producing regions. On the other hand, grape musts are an attractive sugar source due to their glucose and fructose content (about 200 g/L total). Surplus grape musts cause commercial imbalances and economic problems related to unsold wine stocks in producing countries [14]. In Spain, 4,073 ML of wine and 796 ML of grape juice and grape must were produced in 2020 [15]. Therefore, vine shoots and surplus grape must could be explored as feedstocks for biosuccinic acid generation, given their production volume.

The objective of this work was to assess for the first time the suitability of vine shoots and surplus grape must (winery by-products) as feedstocks for succinic acid bioproduction. Two bacterial strains – *Actinobacillus succinogenes* and *Basfia succiniproducens* – were compared in order to select the most appropriate microorganism for each feedstock. In addition, the effect of nutrient supplementation was studied with the twofold purpose of maximizing succinic acid production and discarding unnecessary nutrients. In the case of grape must, several nitrogen sources were tested as microbial nutrients for succinic acid production.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents

All reagents were of analytical grade. Further details about manufacturers and providers can be found in the Supporting Information.

2.2. Feedstocks: winery surplus and by-products

Vine-shoot hydrolysates. Vine shoots were harvested in May 2019 at the experimental plots of ITACyL (Finca Zamadueñas, Valladolid, Spain). They were dried, ground, sieved and analyzed according to Garita-Cambronero et al. [12]. Dry vine shoots contained 32.77% glucan, 11.31% hemicellulose (49.27% total carbohydrates), 2.82% galacturonic acid, 21.30% acid-insoluble lignin, 4.34% protein, 0.52% fat, 7.91% moisture, 2.40% ashes and 13.3 mg/g total phenolic compounds. In order to release the sugars contained in vine shoots, they were subjected to an acidic hydrolysis with 1.72% H₂SO₄ (w/w) at 134 °C for 17 min, with 10% (w/w) solids; followed by an enzymatic hydrolysis for 48 h at 50 °C, 150 rpm and pH 5.0, with the enzyme mixture Cellic CTec2 (Novozymes, Bagsvaerd, Denmark) at a dose of 17.4 FPU per 1 g biomass, as described by Garita-Cambronero et al. [16]. Then, vine-shoot hydrolysates were vacuum-filtered (filter paper No. 1305, Filtros Anioia SA, Barcelona, Spain). The final hydrolysate was analyzed following Paniagua-García et al. [17] and it contained 2.08 g/L cellobiose, 22.43 g/L glucose, 14.09 g/L xylose, 0.48 g/L rhamnose, 1.13 g/L arabinose (40.21 g/L total sugars), 0.11 g/L formic acid, 3.80 g/L acetic acid, 0.11 g/L levulinic acid, 0.40 g/L 5-hydroxy-methyl-furfural, 0.13 g/L furfural and 0.60 g/L total phenolic compounds.

Grape must. Red grape must (variety Garnacha) was obtained in September 2019 from the Oenological

Station of Castile and Leon - ITACyL (Rueda, Spain) and it was kept at -20 °C until use. Grape must was chemically characterized according to Paniagua-García et al. [17]. It had a density of 1.10 g/mL and contained 125 g/L glucose, 119 g/L fructose, 0.34 g/L total Kjeldahl nitrogen and 0.73 g/L total phenolic compounds. Its composition in terms of anions and cations is shown in Table S1.

Wine lees. Two different types of wine lees were collected at the Oenological Station of Castile and Leon - ITACyL (Rueda, Spain) in September-November 2020. Red wine lees had a density of 1.05 g/L and contained 99.3 g/L ethanol, 12.2 g/L total Kjeldahl nitrogen and 1.51 g/L phenolic compounds. White wine lees had a density of 1.03 g/L and contained 81.8 g/L ethanol, 6.8 g/L total Kjeldahl nitrogen and 0.43 g/L phenolic compounds. More information about their chemical characterization is given in Table S1. Wine lees were autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min in order to inactivate residual vinification yeasts. Afterwards, they were sonicated for 30 min at 330 W and 80 kHz in an Elmasonic P 180 H ultrasound bath (Elma Schmidbauer GmbH, Singen, Germany) to provoke cell disruption and release cytoplasmic contents. These treated wine lees were used as nitrogen sources in some fermentation experiments.

2.3. Strain cultivation

The strains *Actinobacillus succinogenes* DSM 22257 and *Basfia succiniproducens* DSM 22022 were obtained from Leibniz Institute DSMZ (Braunschweig, Germany) as freeze-dried cultures. They were reactivated and then cryopreserved as explained in the Supporting Information.

Working inocula were prepared by introducing a loopful of the cryopreserved solutions in a 100-mL glass bottle containing 50 mL tryptic soy broth (pH 7.3). Bottles were capped with a rubber septum and gaseous CO₂ was injected inside the solution for 5 min. Then, the bottles were incubated at 37 °C and 150 rpm for 18-24 h, until an approximate cell density of 5 x 10⁸ cells/mL was attained.

2.4. Fermentation of vine-shoot hydrolysates

Vine-shoot hydrolysates were tested as a feedstock for succinic acid production with two different strains. In the case of *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257, the hydrolysate was enriched with a standard nutrient mix NM-A, composed of 6 g/L yeast extract, 0.2 g/L CaCl₂·2H₂O, 0.2 g/L MgCl₂·6H₂O, 1 g/L NaCl

and 3 g/L K₂HPO₄; and its pH was adjusted to 6.7 with NaOH 50% w/w and NaOH 4 M. In the case of *B. succiniproducens* DSM 22022, the hydrolysates were supplemented with a standard nutrient mix NM-B, which consisted in 5 g/L yeast extract, 2 g/L (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.2 g/L CaCl₂·2H₂O, 0.2 g/L MgCl₂·6H₂O, 2 g/L NaCl and 3 g/L K₂HPO₄; and its pH was adjusted to 6.5. In all cases, the broths were then autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min. In order to maintain a stable pH during the fermentation, solid MgCO₃ was added in an amount of 0.8 g MgCO₃ per 1 g of initial sugars [18].

Fermentations were performed in 100-mL glass bottles containing 50 mL of vine-shoot hydrolysates. The samples were seeded with 5% (v/v) of the inocula described in section 2.3. Then they were closed with rubber caps, gaseous CO₂ was injected in the bottom of the bottles for 5 min to guarantee capnophilic conditions and afterwards the bottles were incubated at 37 °C and 150 rpm in an orbital shaker for 120 h. In addition, control fermentations were performed with synthetic media containing 22 g/L glucose and 14 g/L xylose (similar to the composition of vine-shoot hydrolysates) and supplemented with NM-A for *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 and NM-B for *B. succiniproducens* DSM 22022, respectively. All fermentations were performed in triplicate.

2.5. Preliminary fermentation of grape must

Both bacterial strains were compared in terms of their ability to produce succinic acid from red grape must. In these tests, grape must was diluted with distilled water to obtain a sugar content of 40 g/L (a value similar to that of vine-shoot hydrolysates), but also higher sugar concentrations were assessed (77, 113 and 150 g/L). For *A. succinogenes* grape must was supplemented with NM-A and its pH was set at 6.7, whereas for *B. succiniproducens*, grape must was supplemented with NM-B and its pH was adjusted to 6.5. Samples were autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min, and solid MgCO₃ was added as a pH buffer (0.8 g MgCO₃ per 1 g of initial sugars). Then, samples were inoculated and fermented as described in section 2.4. All fermentations were performed in triplicate for 96 h.

2.6. Improvement of succinic acid production from grape must

The previous experiments with vine shoots and grape must showed that grape must had a great potential for succinic acid production, and that *A.*

succinogenes DSM 2257 had a better performance than *B. succiniproducens* DSM 22022. Therefore, the subsequent experiments were focused on the maximization of succinic acid production with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 from grape must.

In the first place, given the composition of grape must (rich in phosphate, K, Ca and Mg, and short in nitrogen and NaCl; see Table S1), it was decided to determine which nutrients from the NM-A mixture were essential and which nutrients could be ruled out in order to avoid the use of unnecessary reagents during the fermentation and reduce operational costs. A Plackett-Burman experimental design with 12 runs and 5 factors (1-6 g/L yeast extract, 0-0.2 g/L CaCl₂·2H₂O, 0-0.2 g/L MgCl₂·6H₂O, 0-1 g/L NaCl, and 0-3 g/L K₂HPO₄) was performed applying the values shown in Table S2 and starting from a diluted grape must containing 77 g/L initial total sugars. The dependent variable was succinic acid concentration. Samples were fermented for 96 h using MgCO₃ as a pH buffer and according to the conditions described in section 2.4 (except those regarding the standard NM-A addition).

After selecting the indispensable nutrients, their concentrations were optimized by an experimental design based on response surface methodology (RSM) in order to achieve the highest possible concentration of succinic acid. In this case, a complete factorial design, with 13 runs (4 cube points, 5 central points and 4 axial points), 2 factors (initial sugars and yeast extract) and an alpha value of 1.41421, was performed. The concentration of initial sugars ranged from 40 g/L (grape must diluted with water) to 243.46 g/L (undiluted grape must), whereas the concentration of yeast extract ranged from 1 to 40 g/L. The experimental conditions are provided in Table S3. Succinic acid concentration after fermentation was established as the response variable. These results were employed to create an equation to estimate the production of succinic acid from the input values of the independent variables (initial sugars and yeast extract). Then, a mathematical optimum point was calculated in order to maximize succinic acid. In this case, samples were also fermented for 96 h using MgCO₃ as a pH buffer and according to the conditions described in section 2.4 (except those regarding nutrient addition). Control fermentations with glucose-fructose solutions similar to the optimized grape must sample were also performed for comparison purposes.

2.7. Effect of different nitrogen sources on succinic acid production from grape must

The fine-tuning of nutrient concentrations performed in section 2.6 indicated that the optimal values for succinic acid production from grape must were 145.7 g/L initial sugars and 24.9 g/L yeast extract, without any further nutrient addition. Yeast extract was replaced by alternative nitrogen sources in such a way that the total nitrogen (TN) amount added to the fermentation broth was always equivalent. Therefore, yeast extract (TN 11 % w/w), red wine lees (1.22 % TN), white wine lees (0.68 % TN), urea (46.65 % TN), NH₄Cl (26.17 % TN) and choline chloride (10.03 % TN) were added to diluted grape must at concentrations of 24.9, 224.5, 402.8, 5.87, 10.5 and 27.3 g/L, respectively, in order to compare the effect of various nitrogen sources on succinic acid production. In all cases, the initial sugar concentration of grape must was 145.7 g/L. Samples were autoclaved, inoculated with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 (5%, v/v) and their pH was controlled with MgCO₃. Samples were fermented in triplicate under CO₂ atmosphere for 96 h as explained in section 2.4.

2.8. Analysis

Vine-shoot hydrolysates, grape must and fermentation samples were centrifuged at 13,400 × g in a microcentrifuge for 3 min (Minispin, Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The supernatant was filtered through a nylon syringe filter (0.20 μm pore; Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) prior to analysis. Cellobiose, glucose, fructose, xylose, rhamnose, arabinose, succinic acid (SA), formic acid (FA), acetic acid (AA), levulinic acid, lactic acid (LA), ethanol (E), 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF) and furfural were quantified with an Agilent 1200 HPLC equipment (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) provided with a 300 × 7.8 mm i.d. cation exchange column Aminex HPX-87H (Biorad, Hercules, CA, USA) coupled to a refractive index detector (RID, G1362A, Agilent Technologies), using a mobile phase 5 mM H₂SO₄ at a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min and a column temperature of 60 °C [19]. The injection volume was 20 μL.

Sugar consumption during the fermentation process was expressed as a percentage. Succinic acid yield, *Y* (%), was calculated as the ratio between the mass of succinic acid produced (g) and the mass of total sugars consumed (g). Cell density was measured by counting bacteria in a Bürker chamber

(Paul Marienfeld GmbH & Co. KG, Lauda-Königshofen, Germany) using a phase-contrast microscope Leica DM750 (Leica Microsystems SLU, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, Spain).

2.9. Statistics

Comparisons between samples were performed with one-way ANOVA and Tukey's HSD test using the software Statistica 7 (StatSoft Inc., Tulsa, OK, USA). Differences were considered significant when $p < 0.05$. Box-Behnken and RSM experiments were designed with Minitab 16 (Minitab Inc., State College, PA, USA). Curve fitting was performed with SigmaPlot 11 (Systat Software Inc., San José, CA, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Feasibility of succinic acid production from vine shoots

Both *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 and *B. succiniproducens* DSM 22022 were able to grow and produce succinic acid on vine-shoot hydrolysates, which indicates their tolerance to the inhibitors present in this hydrolysate. This fact was especially remarkable for *B. succiniproducens*, whose metabolite production was faster than that of *A. succinogenes* (Figure 1). After 120 h of fermentation, *A. succinogenes* reached 21.18 ± 1.04 g/L succinic acid, whereas *B. succiniproducens* obtained 18.11 ± 1.26 g/L succinic acid, with sugar consumptions above 90 % for both species. This implies succinic acid yields of 0.64 ± 0.04 g/g for *A. succinogenes* and 0.54 ± 0.03 g/g for *B. succiniproducens*. On the contrary, control fermentations (with glucose-xylose solutions) attained 23.15 ± 0.18 g/L succinic acid with *A. succinogenes* (yield 0.70 ± 0.01 g/g) and 19.19 ± 0.60 g/L succinic acid with *B. succiniproducens* (yield 0.62 ± 0.01 g/g) in only 72 h, with sugar consumptions of 95-99 % in both cases.

The nature of vine-shoot hydrolysates influenced the type of secondary metabolites produced by each species. Whereas *A. succinogenes* produced 0.14 ± 0.03 g/L lactic acid, 3.56 ± 0.31 g/L formic acid and 13.99 ± 1.12 g/L acetic acid (148:1:25:98:0, SA:LA:FA:AA:E); *B. succiniproducens* generated 6.83 ± 0.74 g/L lactic acid, 2.19 ± 0.26 g/L formic acid, 8.44 ± 0.24 g/L acetic acid and 0.50 ± 0.21 g/L ethanol (36:14:4:17:1, SA:LA:FA:AA:E) after 120 h (Figure 1). Glucose was consumed faster than xylose by both bacterial species (Figure 1). In fact, Salvachúa et al. [20] had already observed that

glucose consumption by *A. succinogenes* was faster than xylose consumption.

Figure 1. Evolution of succinic acid production in vine-shoot hydrolysates with (A) *Actinobacillus succinogenes* DSM 22257 and (B) *Basfia succiniproducens* DSM 22022. Average values and standard deviations are shown (n = 3). Note: cellobiose, rhamnose and arabinose are not represented in the plots for reasons of simplification.

3.2. Feasibility of succinic acid production from red grape must

Given the nature of grape must, it was possible to assess several initial sugar concentrations (40, 77, 113 and 150 g/L). For both bacterial species, fermentations ended at 96 h and it was observed that sugar consumption decreased as initial sugar concentrations augmented. As shown in Figure 2, the highest succinic acid amount obtained by *A. succinogenes* was 43.25 ± 2.04 g/L and it was recorded when initial sugars were at 113 g/L, consuming 62.19 ± 4.48 % sugars and attaining a yield of 0.67 ± 0.02 g/g. Meanwhile, the highest succinic acid value for *B. succiniproducens* was 33.26 ± 1.06 g/L and it occurred when initial sugars were set at 77 g/L, consuming 100 % sugars and reaching

a yield of 0.46 ± 0.01 g/g (Figure 2). Succinic acid concentrations were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) with *A. succinogenes* than with *B. succiniproducens* for all the initial sugar concentrations tested. For experiments with 113 and 150 g/L, it was observed that fructose consumption was significantly more efficient with *A. succinogenes*, whereas glucose consumption was significantly more efficient with *B. succiniproducens* ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Metabolite production and sugar consumption for various initial sugar concentrations with red grape must after 96 h. (A) *Actinobacillus succinogenes* DSM 22257. (B) *Basfia succiniproducens* DSM 22022. Average values and standard deviations are shown ($n = 3$).

Under the abovementioned conditions of highest succinic acid production (initial sugar concentrations of 113 g/L for *A. succinogenes* and 77 g/L for *B. succiniproducens*), the generation of secondary metabolites was characterized by an important production of lactic acid by *B. succiniproducens*. In brief, this species produced an average of 20.80 ± 1.45 g/L lactic acid, 2.71 ± 1.12 g/L formic acid, 6.16 ± 0.27 g/L acetic acid and 0.71 ± 0.05 g/L ethanol (47:29:4:9:1, SA:LA:FA:AA:E); whereas *A. succinogenes* produced 0.43 ± 0.11 g/L

lactic acid, 5.06 ± 0.59 g/L formic acid, 5.94 ± 0.43 g/L acetic acid and 1.46 ± 0.37 g/L ethanol (100:1:12:14:3, SA:LA:FA:AA:E) (Figure 2). It is worth mentioning that the proportions of secondary metabolites produced from grape must by both species differed from those obtained from vine-shoot hydrolysates (section 3.1).

The best succinic acid values obtained in this work with grape must with both species (33-43 g/L) are clearly higher than those obtained with vine-shoot hydrolysates (18-21 g/L). Accordingly, grape must seems to have a greater potential as a feedstock for succinic acid production and it will be explored in more detail in sections 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5. Moreover, the lower production of secondary metabolites by *A. succinogenes* (especially lactic acid), together with its higher production of succinic acid, make it the species of choice for the next experiments focused on nutrient optimization with grape must.

3.3. Optimization of nutrient addition to grape must for succinic acid production

The results of the Plackett-Burman experiment revealed that yeast extract was the only nutrient in the NM-A mixture which had a significant and positive effect on succinic acid production ($p < 0.05$), while K_2HPO_4 exerted a significantly negative effect (Tables S4-S6). The rest of nutrients ($CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and NaCl) had no statistical effect on the fermentation. Therefore, it would only be necessary to add yeast extract to red grape must in order to produce succinic acid with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257.

The highest succinic acid concentration observed in the Plackett-Burman experimental design was 46.37 g/L (Table S4). However, it is hypothesized that this value could be greatly improved if the concentrations of essential nutrients were optimized (namely, initial sugars and yeast extract), while ruling out unnecessary nutrients (K_2HPO_4 , $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and NaCl).

Consequently, an RSM exploring a sugar range of 40.0-243.5 g/L and a yeast extract range of 1-40 g/L was performed (Table S7). It was observed that succinic acid production and sugar consumption were close to zero for all those experiments with initial sugar concentrations above 200 g/L. The values recorded in the RSM experiment (Tables S7-S10) were employed to create the mathematical model given in Equation (1):

$$\text{Succinic acid } \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{L}}\right) = -92.9158 + 1.6914 s + 5.2417 y - 0.0066 s^2 - 0.1023 y^2 \quad (1)$$

where s and y are the concentrations (g/L) of initial sugars and yeast extract, respectively. Predicted R-squared of the equation was 46.27%. The term sy was not used to calculate the model due to its lack of significance ($p = 0.917$). The model suggests that succinic acid is highly influenced by the nutrient composition of grape must, and that the highest succinic acid values are expected when sugars are in the range of 115-150 g/L and yeast extract is in the range of 20-30 g/L (Figure 3A).

Figure 3. Contour plot for the estimation of (A) succinic acid, and (B) total sugar consumption, as a function of nutrient concentrations (initial sugars and yeast extract), according to the mathematical RSM models for grape must fermented with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257.

The equation was used to optimize the values of the independent variables in order to maximize succinic acid production. Several working conditions were mathematically proposed (Table S11) and then checked experimentally to select the most successful one. Consequently, the model estimated that diluting grape must to 145.7 g/L initial sugars and adding 24.9 g/L yeast extract would allow

obtaining 80.76 g/L succinic acid. These values were tested experimentally and 88.93 ± 1.36 g/L succinic acid were obtained, with a sugar consumption of 96.64 ± 0.30 % and a yield of 0.66 ± 0.01 g/g. Although the estimation of succinic acid was not very accurate as expected from the predicted R-squared value (*i.e.* the experimental value was 10% higher than the modeled response), the optimal point of the RSM represents an extraordinary improvement in comparison to the preliminary tests performed with grape must in section 3.2 (88.93 g/L versus 43.25 g/L succinic acid).

The mathematical model for sugar consumption based on RSM results is shown in Figure 3B, and further details are provided in Tables S12-S14.

3.4. Time evolution of succinic acid production under optimal conditions

After establishing the optimal nutrient composition for grape must, control fermentations with pure glucose and fructose were also performed to evaluate the ability of *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 to grow under similar initial sugar concentrations in the absence of the rest of constituents of grape must. Thus, aqueous solutions containing 72.4 g/L glucose, 73.7 g/L fructose (145.7 g/L total sugars) and 24.9 g/L yeast extract were fermented with and without the addition of NM-A salts (0.2 g/L $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.2 g/L $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1 g/L NaCl and 3 g/L K_2HPO_4). The highest succinic acid production after 96 h corresponded to grape must (85.37 ± 0.69 g/L succinic acid), followed by the control solution with NM-A salts (62.24 ± 2.96 g/L succinic acid), whereas the control solution without salts was not fermentable (3.15 ± 4.28 g/L succinic acid); with significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the three treatments (Figure 4). It is therefore evident that succinic acid production is unviable in the absence of NM-A salts. It is remarkable that metabolite ratios were different in grape must and in the control with NM-A nutrients. Whereas in the grape must 85.37 ± 0.69 g/L succinic acid, 0.66 ± 0.05 g/L lactic acid, 7.68 ± 0.68 g/L formic acid, 13.32 ± 0.38 g/L acetic acid and 0.51 ± 0.31 g/L ethanol (169:1:15:26:1, SA:LA:FA:AA:E) were produced after 96 h; 62.24 ± 2.96 g/L succinic acid, 12.42 ± 14.07 g/L lactic acid, 8.71 ± 0.26 g/L formic acid, 10.51 ± 0.30 g/L acetic acid and 1.45 ± 0.36 g/L ethanol were obtained in the control solution (43:9:6:7:1, SA:LA:FA:AA:E); which is due to the different chemical composition of both samples, as explained in section 4.1. In addition, as highlighted by Brink and Nicol [21],

secondary metabolites such as FA and AA were produced only during the exponential growth phase of microorganisms, while succinic acid was produced during the exponential and stationary phases (Figure 4). It was considered that fermentations had finished after 96 h, reaching sugar consumptions of $93.96 \pm 1.63\%$ in the case of grape must and $91.52 \pm 7.55\%$ in the case of the control solution with NM-A salts (Figure 4). In both cases, the curves for succinic acid production were adjusted to the Hill equation with four parameters ($r^2 > 0.999$), as shown in Table S15.

Figure 4. Time evolution of succinic acid production with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 from 145.7 g/L sugars and 24.9 g/L yeast extract in: (A) grape must, (B) control solution with NM-A salts. Average values and standard deviations are shown ($n = 3$).

3.5. Comparison of nitrogen sources for succinic acid production from grape must

After 96 h of grape-must fermentation, 84.83 ± 2.15 g/L, 3.06 ± 2.58 g/L, 3.50 ± 5.09 g/L, 2.33 ± 0.12 g/L, 0.07 ± 0.12 g/L and 0 ± 0 g/L succinic acid were obtained with yeast extract, red wine lees, white wine lees, urea, NH_4Cl and choline chloride, respectively (Figure S1). Succinic acid production was clearly and statistically higher ($p < 0.05$) with

yeast extract than with any of the other nitrogen sources. Sugar consumption was nil with NH_4Cl and choline chloride (Figure S1). In addition, cell density was statistically similar ($p > 0.11$) and about 10^9 cell/mL for yeast extract, red wine lees and white wine lees, whereas this value was about 10^8 cells/mL for urea, NH_4Cl and choline chloride. The presence of low concentrations of ethanol in the fermentation broths supplemented with wine lees is due to the natural occurrence of this alcohol in lees and not to the fermentative activity of *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 (Figure S1). Consequently, it is evident that yeast extract is the only adequate compound among the nitrogen sources tested for succinic acid production from grape must.

4. Discussion

4.1. Preliminary assessment of vine-shoots and grape must

The amounts of succinic acid produced by both bacterial species (18-21 g/L) from vine-shoot hydrolysates were too low to be attractive from the industrial point of view. This is partly due to the initial sugar concentration of this feedstock (roughly 36 g/L), which is a limiting factor to get higher succinic acid values. Concentrating vine-shoot hydrolysates to obtain higher sugar amounts does not seem energetically advisable. In fact, Filippi et al. [22] concentrated a hydrolysate of grape pomace and grape stalk by evaporation to reach an initial sugar value of 55.7 g/L, whose fermentation with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 led to barely 24.9 g/L succinic acid. Therefore, vine shoots can be discarded as an alternative biomass for succinic acid bioproduction on a large scale. Similarly, the tested bacterial strains obtained 18-24 g/L succinic acid from surplus grape must with similar initial sugar concentrations to vine-shoot hydrolysates (40 g/L sugar) (Figure 2). Nevertheless, succinic acid concentrations raised to 33-43 g/L when sugar concentrations in grape must were increased to 77-113 g/L, thus hinting a possibility of improvement.

The different sugar composition between vine-shoot hydrolysates and grape must could have contributed to their different behavior in succinic acid production and secondary metabolites profile. Vine-shoot hydrolysates contain mainly glucose and xylose, whereas grape must contains glucose and fructose. In fact, metabolite ratios in *A. succinogenes* and *B. succiniproducens* depend on the type of sugars fermented [26], their concentrations [27],

their proportions [28, 29] and the complexity of the broth [30, 31]. Furthermore, *Actinobacillus succinogenes* is known to produce lower succinic acid amounts from xylose than from other sugars, such as glucose, fructose or lactose [23]. In addition, glucose and fructose offer similar succinic acid yields [24] and they are fermented simultaneously by *A. succinogenes* [25].

4.2. Nutrient optimization for grape must

By means of statistical tools, it was possible to discard the addition of conventional *A. succinogenes* nutrients, such as K_2HPO_4 , $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and NaCl, whereas yeast extract was considered essential. This can be explained by the chemical composition of grape must (Table S1), which contains phosphate, K, Ca and Mg in apparently sufficient amounts, but only 0.34 g/L TN. *Actinobacillus succinogenes* is an auxotrophic species that needs vitamins (especially biotin) and fatty acids, which are normally supplemented through yeast extract [1, 3].

The RSM unveiled interesting relationships between variables. Cell density was negatively correlated to initial sugar concentrations ($r^2 = 0.6978$; Table S7). This agrees partly with literature data stating that cell growth of *A. succinogenes* begins to diminish from 60-100 g/L glucose and that it is totally inhibited with about 160 g/L [1, 3]. However, as opposed to the trend observed before nutrient optimization, where sugar consumption declined sharply when initial sugars were above 100 g/L (Figure 2A), the RSM results have shown that sugar consumption can be almost complete even at substrate concentrations of 150 g/L, provided that appropriate yeast extract amounts are supplemented (Table S7). This implies that the growth of *A. succinogenes* under high sugar concentrations in batch fermentations can be ameliorated by an adequate balance of organic nitrogen, thus increasing succinic acid production in a remarkable way. To the best of our knowledge, this phenomenon had never been studied or described before. A wide spectrum of yeast extract supplementation can be found in scientific literature, ranging from 5 g/L [32] to 30 g/L [33], but without establishing any global relationships between yeast extract and substrate consumption.

The beneficial effect of the specific nutrient fine-tuning by RSM on grape must is reflected in Figure 4. The better performance of grape must in

comparison with the control solution with NM-A salts is presumably due to the fact that nutrient concentrations (initial sugars and yeast extract) had been optimized specifically for grape must, whereas the NM-A salts solution can be considered as a non-optimized broth. However, the moderate-high succinic acid values attained with the control solution supplemented with NM-A salts indicate that *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 can cope successfully with high sugar concentrations. In both cases, succinic acid production was negligible during the first 24 h of fermentation (Figure 4), probably due to the adaptation of bacteria to a medium with such a high substrate concentration. The curves of succinic acid and bacterial cell density followed parallel trends but with a time gap: whereas cell density started to rise at $t = 24$ h, succinic acid did at $t = 48$ h (Figure 4). This succinic acid lag phase could be shortened by applying certain techniques, such as cell immobilization [21, 34], large inoculation volumes [35], continuous fermentation [36] or microbial adaptation to high sugar concentrations [37].

4.3. Influence of nitrogen sources on succinic acid production from grape must

Only yeast extract was appropriate for the production of succinic acid with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 from surplus grape must. The addition of wine lees to grape must resulted in an inefficient succinic acid bioproduction (Figure S1). Wine lees contain yeast cellular debris and they have been successfully employed as organic nitrogen sources for succinic acid production [22]. Similar sources of residual fungal biomass, such as spent yeast hydrolysate, dry yeast cells or *Aspergillus* autolysate, have been assessed for succinic acid production with *A. succinogenes*, observing a decrease of 0-40% in succinic acid concentrations or an increase in fermentation times in comparison with commercial yeast extract [23, 24, 38, 39].

Contrarily to what was observed in the present work, urea and inorganic salts, such as KNO_3 , NH_4Cl and $(NH_4)_2SO_4$, have been proved to allow succinic acid production with *A. succinogenes* from agri-food feedstocks, although implying a production decrease of 40-60% compared to yeast extract [24, 40]. In contrast, the inorganic salt $(NH_4)_2HPO_4$ had excellent results for the fermentation of cassava root [6]. Moreover, some vegetal-origin feedstocks have been used for succinic acid production without the addition of any nitrogen source, thanks to their

intrinsic protein content, such as certain fruit juices, juice of oil palm leaves or waste wheat bread [30, 41, 42].

4.4. Feasibility of succinic acid bioproduction from winery surplus and by-products

Table 1 summarizes literature data on batch fermentation processes to obtain succinic acid from industrial, agriculture and food-related feedstocks. According to section 3.1, vine shoots do not seem a good feedstock for succinic acid bioproduction. Apart from the relatively low product concentrations obtained (about 20 g/L succinic acid), the physicochemical and enzymatic pretreatment of vine shoots implies energy and material costs that hinder even more its profitability. This is in agreement with the results observed for other woody materials, such as grape pomace and grape stalk [22] or poplar wood [43], whose succinic acid bioproduction reached 16-25 g/L (Table 1).

On the other hand, grape must presented promising results as a feedstock, with succinic acid values in the range of 84-89 g/L. These high values are related to the initial sugar concentrations employed (145.7 g/L sugars), which did not provoke substrate inhibition thanks to an adequate organic nitrogen balance. The highest succinic acid values obtained so far from agriculture or food-related feedstocks in batch fermentations correspond to cassava root hydrolysate [6], corn stover hydrolysate [39, 44] and ultrafiltered sugarcane molasses [45], reaching 64-93 g/L succinic acid. In fact, the fermentation of grape must has provided the second highest value of succinic acid reported in literature for this type of feedstocks in batch processes (Table 1). Furthermore, grape must does not need any pretreatment before fermentation, apart from diluting with water, which simplifies the process. However, as explained in section 3.3, grape must needs 24.9 g/L yeast extract to maximize succinic acid production, which leads to an increase in production costs, taking into account that the market price of bulk yeast extract in Spain is 5-7.5 €/kg (Vertex Bioenergy, personal communication, June 2021). In any case, Equation (1) enables the calculation of alternative working points with lower yeast extract concentrations which would still provide acceptable succinic acid values (Figure 3). On the contrary, *A. succinogenes* requires almost no external nutrient addition when grown on cassava root hydrolysate or waste bread hydrolysate [6, 30], which makes these feedstocks really attractive for

succinic acid production, provided that they are not detracted from human nutrition (Table 1).

Biosuccinic acid market price is estimated at 3-9 \$/kg depending on its purity and application [46]. In 2015, the fossil-based equivalent was valued at around 2.50 \$/kg [47]. Considering the price of yeast extract and that bulk grape must was sold in Spain for 0.42 €/L [48], the described optimal method to obtain succinic acid from diluted grape must would imply a feedstock cost (grape must and yeast extract) of 4.23-4.93 € per 1 kg of succinic acid in the fermentation stage. If operation costs and recovery and purification costs were included, this price would increase notably, as product recovery from the fermentation broth can account for 50-80 % of the overall process cost [49]. Therefore, succinic acid bioproduction from grape must is currently not very profitable under the given circumstances, although this situation could change in the future depending on the evolution of market prices and available technologies.

Although sugar consumption was almost total with grape must (> 96%), succinic acid yields (0.66 g/g) were far below the theoretical yields of 1.12 g/g from glucose or 1.31 g/g from xylose g/g [50, 51]. This is quite common in batch fermentations (Table 1), because carbon is used not only for succinic acid production, but also for cell growth and for the generation of secondary metabolites. In order to avoid these drawbacks and increase succinic acid production, alternative techniques, such as fed-batch fermentation, continuous fermentation, simultaneous saccharification and fermentation, or cell immobilization, have been assessed with industrial, agriculture and food-related feedstocks, as shown in Table 2. The highest succinic acid concentrations have been reported with cassava root hydrolysate and crude glycerol in fed-batch mode, attaining 150-210 g/L succinic acid [6, 34]. Cell immobilization and continuous fermentation can lead to higher cell concentrations, higher succinic acid concentrations, higher yields, shorter lag phases, shorter fermentation times, lower concentrations of secondary metabolites and therefore higher productivities [1, 41]. Succinic acid bioproduction from alternative feedstocks also needs the development of adequate and economical downstream processes for product recovery and purification [49].

Table 1. Batch fermentations for succinic acid using industrial, agriculture and food-related feedstocks.

Strain	Substrate	Initial sugars (g/L)	Nitrogen source ^(a)	Salts ^(b)	SA (g/L) ^(c)	FA (g/L)	AA (g/L)	PyA (g/L)	PrA (g/L)	LA (g/L)	E (g/L)	Y (g/g)	ΔS (%)	t (h)	Reference
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Jerusalem artichoke (<i>Helianthus tuberosum</i>) hydrolysate	76.5	-	-	47.9	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.67	~ 95	48	[25]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> GXAS137	Duckweed (<i>Landoltia punctata</i>) hydrolysate	64.4	CSL	K ₂ HPO ₄ , NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O, NaCl	57.85	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.89	~ 90	48	[52]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> ATCC 55618	Corn stover hydrolysate	80	YE, CSL	Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaH ₂ PO ₄ , K ₂ HPO ₄ , sodium acetate, NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	43	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.74	-	145	[20]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CGMCC 1716	Corn fiber hydrolysate	70	YE	KH ₂ PO ₄ , MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ , NaCl	~ 48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	48	[23]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CGMCC 1716	Corn fiber hydrolysate	70	Spent yeast cells	KH ₂ PO ₄ , MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ , NaCl, biotin	~ 47	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.68	-	70	[23]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> FZ6 (mutant)	Corn stover hydrolysate	78.9	YE	NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O; Na ₂ HPO ₄ ; biotin	70.6	0.3	2.8	-	3	-	-	0.88	-	101	[44]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CGMCC 1716	Corn stover hydrolysate	100	YE, CSL	KH ₂ PO ₄ , MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ , NaCl	67.53	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	~ 97	70	[39]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CGMCC 1593	Corn stover hydrolysate	58	YE	NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O, K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	45.5	~ 1	~ 5	-	-	-	-	0.81	~ 100	48	[18]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CCTCC M 2011399	Sugarcane juice	70	-	K ₂ HPO ₄ , NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O, NaCl	57.11	-	~ 7	-	-	-	-	-	~ 95	48	[40]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CGMCC 1593	Sugarcane molasses (inverted)	64.4	YE	Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O, NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O, NaCl, MgCl ₂ , CaCl ₂	46.4	~ 2	~ 7	-	-	-	-	0.79	~ 90	48	[24]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Sugarcane molasses (ultrafiltration)	60	YE, CSL	NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O, MnCl ₂ , sodium acetate, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaH ₂ PO ₄ , K ₂ HPO ₄	64.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	28	[45]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> ATCC 55618	Wheat flour hydrolysate	70	YE	NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	35.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.82	~ 61	~ 65	[38]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Grape pomace and grape stalk hydrolysate	55.7	Wine lees	NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	24.9	7.2	9.1	-	-	-	-	0.59	~ 91	40	[22]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Alga (<i>Saccharina latissima</i>) hydrolysate	~ 55	YE	K ₂ HPO ₄ , MgCl ₂ , CaCl ₂ , NaCl	36.8	1.4	7.9	-	-	-	1	-	100	48	[53]

Strain	Substrate	Initial sugars (g/L)	Nitrogen source ^(a)	Salts ^(b)	SA (g/L) ^(c)	FA (g/L)	AA (g/L)	PyA (g/L)	PrA (g/L)	LA (g/L)	E (g/L)	Y (g/g)	ΔS (%)	t (h)	Reference
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Pineapple juice	56.2	-	-	37	1.2	6.1	-	-	-	-	1.00	65	~ 168	[41]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Lemon-lime softdrink (hydrolysate)	36.1	YE	NaCl, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaH ₂ PO ₄ , K ₂ HPO ₄ , MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	40.4	3.1	7.5	-	-	-	-	1.11	100	~ 120	[41]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Almond syrup (hydrolysate)	42.4	YE	NaCl, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaH ₂ PO ₄ , K ₂ HPO ₄ , MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	45.3	2.1	7.5	-	-	-	-	1.10	95	~ 130	[41]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> ATCC 55618	Cassava root hydrolysate	150	(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	-	93.34	~ 0	~ 20	~ 55	-	~ 0	-	0.77	-	50	[6]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Alga (<i>Laminaria digitata</i>) hydrolysate	45	YE	K ₂ HPO ₄ , MgCl ₂ , CaCl ₂ , NaCl	33.78	~ 4	~ 8	-	-	~ 4	~ 0.1	0.63	-	48	[54]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> ATCC 55618	Waste wheat bread hydrolysate	40	-	-	47.3	0	0.2	0	-	-	-	1.16	100	60	[30]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Vine shoot hydrolysate	36.1	YE	CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, NaCl, K ₂ HPO ₄	21.18	3.56	13.99	-	-	0.14	-	0.64	91.24	120	This work
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Grape must	145.7	YE	-	88.93	7.3	12.7	-	-	0.48	0.84	0.66	96.64	96	This work
<i>B. succiniciproducens</i> CCUG 57335	Corn stover hydrolysate	60	YE, CSL, (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	K ₂ HPO ₄ , NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	30.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	72	[26]
<i>B. succiniciproducens</i> BPP7	Poplar (<i>Populus nigra</i>) hydrolysate	20-23	YE, (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	CaCl ₂ ·H ₂ O, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, NaCl, K ₂ HPO ₄	16.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.75	100	30	[43]
<i>B. succiniciproducens</i> DSM 22022	Spent sulphite liquor (diluted, ultrafiltered)	18	YE	NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	8.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.52	-	~ 15	[31]
<i>Escherichia coli</i> SD121 (modified)	Corn stover hydrolysate	44	YE, tryptone, (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O, Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O, NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O, CaCl ₂	36.55	-	4	-	-	-	-	0.83	~ 100	84	[55]
<i>E. coli</i> MG-PYC (modified)	Licorice waste (<i>Glycyrrhiza uralensis</i>) hydrolysate	58	YE	MgSO ₄ , K ₂ HPO ₄ , KH ₂ PO ₄ , NaCl, MnCl ₂ , CaCl ₂	35	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.69	~ 88	60	[56]
<i>Yarrowia lipolytica</i> PSA02004 (modified)	Municipal organic waste hydrolysate	120	YE, tryptone	Na ₂ HPO ₄	42.2	-	6.8	-	-	-	-	0.38	-	~ 50	[5]

(a) CSL: corn steep liquor, YE: yeast extract. (b) The pH-buffer MgCO₃ is not included as a nutritive salt. (c) SA: succinic acid, FA: formic acid; AA: acetic acid, PyA: pyruvic acid, PrA: propionic acid, LA: lactic acid, E: ethanol, Y: succinic acid yield, ΔS: total sugar consumption.

Table 2. Fed-batch, immobilisation and other alternative fermentation types for succinic acid using industrial, agriculture and food-related feedstocks.

Strain	Substrate	Initial sugars (g/L)	Nitrogen source (a)	Salts (b)	Fermentation type (c)	SA (g/L) (d)	FA (g/L)	AA (g/L)	PyA (g/L)	LA (g/L)	E (g/L)	Y (g/g)	t (h)	Reference
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CGMCC 1593	Corn stover hydrolysate	40	YE	NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O, K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	FB	53.2	~ 0	~ 5	-	-	-	0.825	44	[18]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CCTCC M 2011399	Sugarcane juice	70	-	K ₂ HPO ₄ , NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O, NaCl	FB	62.1	-	~ 7	-	-	-	-	48	[40]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CGMCC 1593	Sugarcane molasses (inverted)	35	YE	Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O, NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O, NaCl, MgCl ₂ , CaCl ₂	FB	55.2	~ 3	~ 7	-	-	-	-	48	[24]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Grape pomace and grape stalk hydrolysate	40.1	Wine lees	NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	FB	37.2	6	9.2	-	-	-	0.64	47	[22]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> ATCC 55618	Cassava root hydrolysate	70	(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	-	FB	151.4	-	-	1	-	-	~ 1.5	48	[6]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	Sugarcane molasses (ultrafiltered)	60	YE, CSL	NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O, MnCl ₂ , sodium acetate, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaH ₂ PO ₄ , K ₂ HPO ₄	B, I	45.6	-	-	-	-	-	0.76	24	[45]
<i>A. succinogenes</i> CGMCC1593	Corn stover hydrolysate	-	CSL	Sodium acetate, K ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O, NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O, MgCl ₂ , CaCl ₂	B, SSF	47.4	~ 2	~ 10	-	~ 2	-	0.72	48	[58]
<i>B. succiniciproducens</i> DSM 22022	Spent sulphite liquor (diluted, nanofiltered)	18	YE	NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O, Na ₂ HPO ₄ , NaCl, MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	FB	33.8	-	-	-	-	-	0.58	~ 70	[31]
<i>Corynebacterium glutamicum</i> 534 (mutant)	Cassava bagasse hydrolysate	35	-	NaCl	B, I	22.4	-	9.2	-	3.7	-	0.648	54	[57]
<i>E. coli</i> SD121 (modified)	Corn stover hydrolysate	44	YE, tryptone, (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O, Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O, NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O, CaCl ₂	FB	57.8	-	8.17	-	-	1.62	0.87	72	[55]
<i>E. coli</i> MG-PYC (modified)	Licorice waste (<i>Glycyrrhiza uralensis</i>) hydrolysate	45	YE	MgSO ₄ , K ₂ HPO ₄ , KH ₂ PO ₄ , NaCl, MnCl ₂ , CaCl ₂	FB	65	-	-	-	-	-	0.89	128	[56]
<i>Y. lipolytica</i> PGC01003 (modified)	Crude glycerol	120	YE, peptone	-	B, I	53.6	-	-	-	-	-	0.45	37	[34]
<i>Y. lipolytica</i> PGC01003 (modified)	Crude glycerol	120	YE, peptone	-	FB, I	209.7	-	~ 3	-	-	-	-	322	[34]
<i>Y. lipolytica</i> PSA02004 (modified)	Municipal organic waste hydrolysate	120	YE	-	FB	54.4	-	3	-	-	-	0.44	~ 66	[5]

(a) CSL: corn steep liquor, YE: yeast extract. (b) The pH-buffer MgCO₃ is not included as a nutritive salt. (c) B: batch, FB: fed-batch, I: immobilisation, SSF: simultaneous saccharification and fermentation. (d) SA: succinic acid, FA: formic acid; AA: acetic acid, PyA: pyruvic acid, LA: lactic acid, E: ethanol, Y: succinic acid yield.

Accordingly, further research on genetic engineering, cell cultivation, nutrient optimization, fermentation technologies and recovery processes could make grape must a suitable feedstock for industrial succinic acid bioproduction in the future

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Permission statements

The manuscript does not contain experiments using animals. The manuscript does not contain human studies.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information includes data on reagents, strain activation and storage, feedstock composition, statistical nutrient optimization, kinetics and effect of nitrogen sources.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Assessment of vine shoots and surplus grape must for succinic acid bioproduction

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Index

Reagents	18
Strain reactivation and storage	18
Feedstock composition	18
Table S1. Contents of anions and cations in grape must and wine lees.	18
Nutrient optimisation experiments	18
Table S2. Ranges used for the independent variables in the Plackett-Burman experiment ...	18
Table S3. Experimental conditions assessed with the RSM design	19
Table S4. Experimental conditions of the Plackett-Burman design and response values	19
Table S5. Effect of each independent variable on the response variable (succinic acid concentration) in the Plackett-Burman experimental design	19
Table S6. Unusual observations for succinic acid in the Plackett-Burman experiment.	19
Table S7. Experimental conditions tested in the RSM design and fermentation responses ...	20
Table S8. Estimated regression coefficients for Succinic Acid (g/L) in the RSM experiment with grape must and <i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	20
Table S9. Analysis of variance of Succinic Acid (g/L) in the RSM experiment with grape must and <i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	20
Table S10. Unusual observations for Succinic Acid (g/L) in the RSM experiment with grape must and <i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	21
Table S11. Optimal values of nutrients calculated according to the RSM model	21
Table S12. Estimated regression coefficients for Total Sugar Consumption (%) in the RSM experiment with grape must and <i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257 after 96 h	21
Table S13. Analysis of variance of Total Sugar Consumption (%) in the RSM experiment with grape must and <i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	22
Table S14. Unusual observations for Total Sugar Consumption (%) in the RSM experiment with grape must and <i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	22
Kinetics of grape must fermentation	22
Table S15. Kinetics of succinic acid production from grape must and control medium with <i>Actinobacillus succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	22
Comparison of nitrogen sources for succinic acid production from grape must	23
Figure S1. Effect of nitrogen sources on the 96-h fermentation of grape must with <i>A. succinogenes</i> DSM 22257	23

Reagents

The compounds D-(+)-glucose, D-(-)-fructose, D-(+)-xylose and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Steinheim, Germany); yeast extract and NaCl were supplied by Fluka Analytical - Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Steinheim, Germany); K_2HPO_4 , urea and NaOH were obtained from Panreac Química SLU (Castellar del Vallès, Spain); $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and choline chloride were manufactured by Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium), $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was purchased from Fisher Scientific (Geel, Belgium); NH_4Cl was produced by VWR Chemicals (Leuven, Belgium); whereas MgCO_3 was supplied by Honeywell (Seelze, Germany).

Strain reactivation and storage

For reactivation, both strains (*Actinobacillus succinogenes* DSM 22257 and *Basfia succiniproducens* DSM 22022) were resuspended in 1 mL of brain heart broth (Biokar Diagnostics, Allone, France). A volume of 200 μL of this suspension was added to 50 mL of tryptic soy broth (Becton, Dickinson and Company; Le Pont de Claix, France) in a rubber-capped 100-mL glass bottle. Gaseous CO_2 was bubbled into the bottom of the bottle for 5 min before a incubation at 37 °C and 150 rpm for 24 h in an Infors HT Ecotron orbital shaker (Infors AG, Bottmingen, Switzerland). These samples were preserved at -80 °C in cryovials with 17% (v/v) glycerol as bacterial stocks.

Feedstock composition

Table S1. Contents of anions and cations in grape must and wine lees.

	Red grape must	Red wine lees	White wine lees
Chloride (mg/L)	29	31	16
Fluoride (mg/L)	28	19	54
Phosphate (mg/L)	185	1180	477
Nitrate (mg/L)	1	13	14
Nitrite (mg/L)	<1	<1	<1
Sulphate (mg/L)	49	334	334
Bromide (mg/L)	<1	<1	<1
Sodium (mg/L)	3	21	14.4
Potassium (mg/L)	1447	7560	13184
Calcium (mg/L)	143.5	251.2	213.0
Magnesium (mg/L)	81.9	185.6	92.9
Iron (mg/L)	<0.10	18.7	1.29
Manganese (mg/L)	0.16	3.63	4.47
Zinc (mg/L)	0.20	5.43	2.25
Copper (mg/L)	<0.04	11.2	5.13

Nutrient optimisation experiments

Table S2. Ranges used for the five independent variables in the Plackett-Burman experiment with grape must (77 g/L initial sugars) and *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257.

	Minimum	Maximum
Yeast extract (g/L)	1	6
$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (g/L)	0	0.2
$\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (g/L)	0	0.2
NaCl (g/L)	0	1
K_2HPO_4 (g/L)	0	3

Table S3. Experimental conditions assessed with the RSM design for succinic acid production from grape must using *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257.

Run	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Initial sugars (g/L)	213.7	141.7	213.7	69.8	141.7	141.7	40.0	69.8	141.7	243.5	141.7	141.7	141.7
Yeast extract (g/L)	34.3	1.0	6.7	6.7	20.5	20.5	20.5	34.3	20.5	20.5	20.5	20.5	40.0

Table S4. Experimental conditions of the Plackett-Burman design, and response values obtained for each condition during the 96-h fermentation of grape must (initial sugars 77 g/L) with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257.

Run	Independent variables					Responses										
	Yeast extract (g/L)	CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (g/L)	MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O (g/L)	NaCl (g/L)	K ₂ HPO ₄ (g/L)	SA (g/L)	LA (g/L)	FA (g/L)	AA (g/L)	E (g/L)	CD (x10 ⁹ cells/mL)	pH final	ΔG (%)	ΔF (%)	ΔS (%)	Y (g/g)
1	1	0	0.2	1	3	9.31	0.12	2.83	2.21	1.53	0.33	7.23	25.22	28.71	26.96	0.483
2	1	0	0	0	0	13.83	0.17	3.12	1.81	2.11	0.63	6.99	32.04	43.63	37.78	0.499
3	1	0.2	0.2	0	3	8.85	0.13	2.43	1.61	1.38	0.63	7.15	27.53	25.91	26.72	0.454
4	6	0.2	0	1	3	35.09	0.33	6.22	6.04	1.95	1.98	6.30	84.79	85.62	85.20	0.556
5	1	0.2	0	0	0	17.86	0.21	3.47	1.87	2.10	0.73	7.00	39.05	54.34	46.66	0.509
6	1	0	0	1	3	13.04	0.13	2.79	1.71	1.92	0.73	7.06	30.95	42.02	36.47	0.483
7	6	0.2	0	1	0	42.88	0.31	5.25	6.81	1.00	1.65	6.73	97.56	97.65	97.60	0.591
8	6	0	0.2	0	0	43.34	0.34	6.03	7.01	1.33	1.85	6.74	100.0	100.0	100.0	0.572
9	6	0	0.2	1	0	46.37	0.32	4.54	6.34	0.68	1.45	6.73	100.0	100.0	100.0	0.623
10	6	0	0	0	3	38.65	0.33	5.55	6.09	1.77	1.68	6.46	92.62	92.94	92.78	0.567
11	6	0.2	0.2	0	3	32.93	0.33	6.40	6.08	2.24	1.26	6.44	78.31	86.57	82.45	0.531
12	1	0.2	0.2	1	0	16.22	0.17	3.18	2.00	1.74	0.54	7.01	33.85	49.58	41.68	0.519

Notes: YE: yeast extract; SA: succinic acid; LA: lactic acid; FA: formic acid; AA: acetic acid; E: ethanol; CD: cell density; ΔG: glucose consumption; ΔF: fructose consumption; ΔS: total sugar consumption; Y: succinic acid yield.

Table S5. Effect of each independent variable on the response variable (succinic acid concentration) in the Plackett-Burman experimental design with grape must (initial sugars 77 g/L) fermented by *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 for 96 h.

Term	Effect	Coefficient (coded)	SE Coef.	T	p
Constant		26.531	0.6869	38.62	0.000
Yeast extract (g/L)	26.692	13.346	0.6869	19.43	0.000
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (g/L)	-1.785	-0.892	0.6869	-1.30	0.242
MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O (g/L)	-0.722	-0.361	0.6869	-0.53	0.618
NaCl (g/L)	1.242	0.621	0.6869	0.90	0.401
K ₂ HPO ₄ (g/L)	-7.105	-3.553	0.6869	-5.17	0.002
S = 2.37955		PRESS = 135.894			
R-square = 98.55%		R-square (pred.) = 94.19%		R-square (adjusted) = 97.34%	

Table S6. Unusual observations for succinic acid (g/L) in the Plackett-Burman experiment.

Run	Succinic acid (g/L)	Fit	SE Fit	Residue	Std. Residue	
2	13.8300	17.3700	1.6826	-3.5400	-2.10	R

R denotes an observation with a large standardized residue.

Table S7. Experimental conditions tested in the RSM design and fermentation responses observed for each condition during the 96-h transformation of grape must with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257.

Run	Independent variables (factors)		Dependent variables (responses observed)										
	Initial sugars (g/L)	YE (g/L)	SA (g/L)	LA (g/L)	FA (g/L)	AA (g/L)	E (g/L)	CD (x10 ⁹ cells/mL)	pH final	ΔG (%)	ΔF (%)	ΔS (%)	Y (g/g)
1	213.7	34.3	6.31	0.11	2.57	3.75	<0.05	1.05	6.85	2.24	3.51	2.89	1.069
2	141.7	1	6.03	<0.05	3.58	3.42	<0.05	0.66	7.13	5.05	12.96	8.95	0.468
3	213.7	6.7	0.43	<0.05	0.22	0.39	<0.05	0.59	7.62	2.37	3.20	2.78	0.075
4	69.8	6.7	38.48	0.25	4.98	6.40	0.84	4.30	6.52	82.43	83.16	82.79	0.656
5	141.7	20.5	80.63	0.88	7.30	11.07	0.81	3.50	6.86	94.58	96.48	95.53	0.596
6	141.7	20.5	80.2	0.88	7.38	10.48	<0.05	3.50	6.94	91.36	95.69	93.53	0.608
7	40.0	20.5	24.6	0.23	4.94	7.80	0.55	5.15	6.15	98.61	100.0	99.31	0.590
8	69.8	34.3	41.11	0.52	6.63	10.90	0.62	4.95	6.49	99.64	100.0	99.82	0.664
9	141.7	20.5	79.7	1.23	7.83	11.14	0.54	4.15	6.98	91.30	96.24	93.78	0.601
10	243.5	20.5	4.53	0.10	1.15	1.05	<0.05	1.43	7.71	2.57	3.08	2.83	0.698
11	141.7	20.5	78.04	1.60	7.20	10.80	0.94	3.25	6.93	85.22	84.11	84.66	0.633
12	141.7	20.5	76.09	0.78	8.96	13.38	0.88	3.2	7.11	82.27	91.21	86.75	0.616
13	141.7	40.0	81.63	1.10	8.79	14.08	<0.05	3.30	6.92	95.67	86.66	91.03	0.653

Notes: YE: yeast extract; SA: succinic acid; LA: lactic acid; FA: formic acid; AA: acetic acid; E: ethanol; CD: cell density; ΔG: glucose consumption; ΔF: fructose consumption; ΔS: total sugar consumption; Y: succinic acid yield.

Table S8. Estimated regression coefficients for Succinic Acid (g/L) in the RSM experiment with grape must and *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257. Note: The term Initial sugars*Yeast extract (A x B) was removed from the model due to its high *p* value (*p* = 0.917).

Term	Coefficient	Standard error coef.	T	p
Constant	-92.9158	24.1473	-3.848	0.005
Initial sugars (g/L)	1.6914	0.3009	5.621	0.000
Yeast extract (g/L)	5.2417	1.2081	4.339	0.002
Initial sugars (g/L) * Initial sugars (g/L)	-0.0066	0.0010	-6.377	0.000
Yeast extract (g/L) * Yeast extract (g/L)	-0.1023	0.0281	-3.640	0.007
S = 14.0986	PRESS= 7637.65			
R-square = 88.81%	R-square (predicted) = 46.27%	R-square (adjusted) = 83.22%		

Table S9. Analysis of variance of Succinic Acid (g/L) in the RSM experiment with grape must and *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257. Note: The term Initial sugars*Yeast extract (A x B) was removed from the model due to its high *p* value (*p* = 0.917).

Source	df	Sum of squares Seq.	Sum of squares Adjust.	Mean squares Adjust.	F	p
Regression	4	12623.6	12623.6	3155.89	15.88	0.001
Lineal	2	2946.4	8979.7	4489.85	22.59	0.001
Initial sugars (g/L)	1	1281.0	6280.2	6280.15	31.59	0.000
Yeast extract (g/L)	1	1665.4	3742.1	3742.09	18.83	0.002
Quadratic	2	9677.2	9677.2	4838.60	24.34	0.000
Initial sugars (g/L) * Initial sugars (g/L)	1	7044.2	8083.1	8083.07	40.67	0.000
Yeast extract (g/L) * Yeast extract (g/L)	1	2633.0	2633.0	2632.96	13.25	0.007
Residual error	8	1590.2	1590.2	198.77		
Lack of fit	4	1576.2	1576.2	394.05	112.96	0.000
Pure error	4	14.0	14.0	3.49		
Total	12	14213.7				

Table S10. Unusual observations for Succinic Acid (g/L) in the RSM experiment with grape must and *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257.

Run	Succinic acid (g/L)	Fit	SE Fit	Resid.	Std. Resid.	
13	81.630	60.427	11.146	21.203	2.46	R

R denotes an observation with a large standardized residue.

Table S11. Optimal values of nutrients calculated according to the RSM model for the maximisation of succinic acid production from grape must with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 after 96 h of fermentation. *Note:* Three different optimal points proposed by the model (A, B and C) were executed and compared in order to select the most appropriate one.

Point	Independent variables (RSM model)		Estimated response	Experimental responses (n = 3)										
	Initial sugars (g/L)	YE (g/L)		SA (g/L)	SA (g/L)	LA (g/L)	FA (g/L)	AA (g/L)	E (g/L)	CD (x10 ⁹ cells/mL)	pH final	ΔG (%)	ΔF (%)	ΔS (%)
A	128.4	25.4	82.78	79.02 ± 0.66	0.40 ± 0.02	7.50 ± 0.26	13.22 ± 0.19	0.69 ± 0.19	3.83 ± 0.25	6.87 ± 0.07	100 ± 0	95.57 ± 0.46	97.96 ± 0.23	0.65 ± 0.01
B	108.5	25.8	80.17	68.82 ± 1.18	0.39 ± 0.04	7.85 ± 0.33	13.29 ± 0.23	0.47 ± 0.07	3.75 ± 0.23	6.72 ± 0.04	100 ± 0	96.39 ± 0.29	98.18 ± 0.14	0.66 ± 0.01
C	145.7	24.9	80.76	88.93 ± 1.36	0.48 ± 0.06	7.31 ± 0.15	12.71 ± 0.14	0.84 ± 0.18	2.52 ± 0.55	6.94 ± 0.03	99.63 ± 0.64	93.70 ± 0.50	96.64 ± 0.30	0.66 ± 0.01

Notes: YE: yeast extract; SA: succinic acid; LA: lactic acid; FA: formic acid; AA: acetic acid; E: ethanol; CD: cell density; ΔG: glucose consumption; ΔF: fructose consumption; ΔS: total sugar consumption; Y: succinic acid yield.

Table S12. Estimated regression coefficients for Total Sugar Consumption (%) in the RSM experiment with grape must and *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 after 96 h. *Note:* The term Initial sugars*Yeast extract (A x B) was removed from the model due to its high *p* value (*p* = 0.587).

Term	Coefficient	Standard error coef.	T	p
Constant	15.6299	24.3481	0.642	0.539
Initial sugars (g/L)	0.5925	0.3034	1.953	0.087
Yeast extract (g/L)	5.7999	1.2181	4.761	0.001
Initial sugars (g/L) *	-0.0040	0.0010	-3.851	0.005
Initial sugars (g/L)				
Yeast extract (g/L) *	-0.1120	0.0283	-3.951	0.004
Yeast extract (g/L)				
S = 14.2158	PRESS= 7351.25			
R-square = 92.50%	R-square (predicted) = 65.89%	R-square (adjusted) = 88.75%		

Table S13. Analysis of variance of Total Sugar Consumption (%) in the RSM experiment with grape must and *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257. *Note:* The term Initial sugars*Yeast extract (A x B) was removed from the model due to its high *p* value (*p* = 0.587).

Source	df	Sum of squares Seq.	Sum of squares Adjust.	Mean squares Adjust.	F	p
Regression	4	19937.3	19937.3	4984.34	24.66	0.000
Lineal	2	14495.2	4969.8	2484.90	12.30	0.004
Initial sugars (g/L)	1	12276.7	770.6	770.57	3.81	0.087
Yeast extract (g/L)	1	2218.4	4581.5	4581.45	22.67	0.001
Quadratic	2	5442.2	5442.2	2721.09	13.46	0.003
Initial sugars (g/L) * Initial sugars (g/L)	1	2287.6	2997.1	2997.13	14.83	0.005
Yeast extract (g/L) * Yeast extract (g/L)	1	3154.6	3154.6	3154.61	15.61	0.004
Residual error	8	1616.7	1616.7	202.09		
Lack of fit	4	1524.0	1524.0	380.99	16.43	0.009
Pure error	4	92.8	92.8	23.19		
Total	12	21554.1				

Table S14. Unusual observations for Total Sugar Consumption (%) in the RSM experiment with grape must and *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257.

Run	Total sugar consumption (%)	Fit	SE Fit	Resid.	Std. Resid.	
1	2.889	26.278	8.705	-23.389	-2.08	R
13	91.030	71.812	11.239	19.219	2.21	R

R denotes an observation with a large standardized residue.

Kinetics of grape must fermentation

Table S15. Kinetics of succinic acid production from grape must and control medium with *Actinobacillus succinogenes* DSM 22257, based on data from Figure 4. All curves were fitted to Hill equation with four parameters:

$$C_{SA} = y_0 + \frac{at^b}{c^b + t^b}$$

where C_{SA} is succinic acid concentration (g/L) and t is fermentation time.

Sample	Equation parameters				
	a	b	c	y_0	R-square
Grape must	87.5914	5.4355	46.0411	-0.8291	0.9997
Control with NM-A salts	67.8466	5.1763	57.7376	-0.3641	0.9998

Comparison of nitrogen sources for succinic acid production from grape must

Figure S1. Effect of nitrogen sources on the 96-h fermentation of grape must with *A. succinogenes* DSM 22257 (145.7 g/L initial sugars and 2.74 g/L total nitrogen). Average values and standard deviations are shown (n = 3).